

Does Shannon's Entropy for an Ideal Gas Follow From Free Particle Quantum Mechanics?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 23, 2026

We have argued in previous notes that $C(T) \exp(-E_i/T)$ (the Maxwell-Boltzmann probability) and $\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$ (the free particle quantum probability called a wavefunction) have the same informational structure in that product probabilities for a given $E_1 = E_i + E_j$ for the MB case and E_i, p_i and E_j, p_j for the quantum case lead to uniform distributions, i.e. ones with minimal information if energy and momentum are conserved. We suggest here that the root for this may be same.

We have argued in previous notes that $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ cannot have dt be infinitesimally small. This means that there exists a scale at which dt is not 0 or even tiny. We also suggested that the force (even though obeying action-reaction in collisions) may strike at some probabilistic time within dt . We then used special relativity to find that $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dp = \hbar/p$. A probability which demonstrates these gradations is $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ (and also Lorentz invariant). This is akin to the notion that $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ and $p(p_1)p(p_2) = p(p_3)p(p_4)$ (one dimension for simplicity). In other words, the stochasticity introduced is one of a uniform distribution for product probabilities. One could obtain the same result by starting with this assumption and then suggesting Lorentz invariance.

We suggest that this quantum uniform distribution product probability also holds for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. There, the probability is not complex because $p(e_i)$ must be a real number linked to the number of particles with e_i . Nevertheless, in an elastic collision of e_i and e_j , we suggest that the quantum result (and even $dp/dt = F$) suggest that there is stochasticity in x and t and that one cannot deterministically predict the outcome. Any outcome which conserves energy and momentum has the same likelihood. We suggest that it is the quantum mechanical assumption which is identical to the ideal gas case (which uses quantum mechanical gas molecules albeit at high temperatures). The high temperatures mean that one can only use the conservation laws and the associated stochasticity.

We suggest that the stochasticity of interaction inherent in quantum mechanics carries over to collisions in the classical gas. It is not simply that one is approximating the situation in a gas by throwing away information. If one were to try to be as deterministic as possible at some scale (the quantum one) stochasticity arises and there is no full determinism in a collision. The best one can do is use conservation of momentum and sometimes conservation of energy in certain situations like high temperature.

If this is the case, one may ask: Why is it possible to perform deterministic classical calculations such as particles bouncing off walls or mirrors or interacting with a potential $V(x)$ in a completely deterministic manner. We suggest that these involve constrained interactions, i.e. the wall or $V(x)$ is associated with a huge mass compared to the particle, unlike in a collision of two identical particles. Action-reaction in the former case is associated with the large mass and so always the same approximately 0 kinetic energy and hence no $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$, but in the latter, with a mass the same size and so the stochasticity may be seen clearly.

Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

We have suggested obtaining the complex probability $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$ (called a wavefunction) in two ways. The first is to consider Newton's second law:

$$dp/dt = \text{Force} \quad ((1))$$

We argue that dt is finite, although very tiny. In interactions, action-reaction applies to the force, but we suggest that given a finite dt , one does not really know at which t in dt the force will strike. In other words, there is stochasticity which carries over to dx as well. Given that $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ is directly linked to special relativity because a particle at rest is seen as moving with v by a frame moving with $-v$, this means $\text{Force} = dp/dt$ must have acted on the particle. We thus seek dt and dx from special relativity.

Using the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

One sees that $t + \hbar/E$ and $x + \hbar/p$ leave A unchanged. $((3))$

We suggest that x, t in $((2))$ represents the $x = vt$ trajectory, but that interaction acts may occur off the x, t of the center of mass point, i.e. within $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$. Given that a free particle has no real probability weight because nothing is being distributed to it in a collection (there is no collection), we seek an $\exp(i f(x)) \exp(i g(t))$ which manifests dx and dt . A Lorentz invariant solution is:

$$\exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad ((3))$$

$((3))$ in turn leads to the stochastic product distribution:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \text{ if } e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \text{ and } p(p_1)p(p_2) = p(p_3)p(p_4) \text{ if } p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4 \text{ (one dimension)} \quad ((4))$$

Thus, a very specific kind of stochasticity (i.e. a least information one arises).

One may arrive at $((3))$ in a different manner. One may consider elastic collisions and argue a priori that given an e_1, e_2 and p_1, p_2 , any outcome e_i, e_j, p_i, p_j which add to $e_1 + e_2$ and $p_1 + p_2$ (one dimension) have the same weight as one cannot really be deterministic to $dx = 0$ and $dt = 0$. This leads to:

$$\exp(iC_1E) \text{ and } \exp(iC_2p) \quad ((5))$$

Making $((5))$ Lorentz invariant yields $((3))$

In other words, quantum mechanics dictates that there is stochasticity in free particle interactions and so at a certain scale one cannot have determinism. One could, however, have a full quantum treatment as in the case of a particle quantum mechanically interacting with 2-slits or a potential. If, however, temperatures are high, we argue that wavelengths are small and that one can use $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$ from the quantum case as describing the full uncertainty present.

Ideal Gas

An ideal gas consists of molecules which are in fact quantum mechanical. At high temperatures, it is argued that one may consider classical collisions (i.e ignore $V(x)$ and the wavefunction interaction). We argue that this does not mean that one can now predict the outcome of an elastic collision of e_1, e_2, p_1, p_2 . One still has the uncertainty discussed above. One just does not need to perform a quantum mechanical analysis using $V(x)$ and the Schrodinger equation as in scattering theory. Nevertheless, free particle quantum mechanics introduces uncertainty into the collision of the form:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j) \text{ for } e_1+e_2 = e_i+e_j \quad ((4))$$

In a gas, there is a collection and total energy is being distributed so $p(e_i)$ cannot be $\exp(-C_1 e_i)$, but must be a real number. Nevertheless, ((4)) must hold from the quantum mechanical ideas. Thus,

$$p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T) , \text{ the Maxwell-Boltzmann result } ((5))$$

From ((5)), one may create a math function $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ which when maximized subject to $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ with $-1/T$ as the Lagrange multiplier yields ((5)). The root of the entropy, i.e. loss of knowledge comes from the quantum mechanical viewpoint in which there must be stochasticity in an interaction at some small scale.

Deterministic Newtonian Mechanics

If the above ideas about stochasticity in interaction hold, how is it possible to have deterministic classical Newtonian calculations? For example, a ball bouncing off a mirror or the floor is treated in a completely deterministic manner as is a trajectory in a potential $V(x)$. We argue that in such a case, one participant in the interaction is very large (with a very large mass). In such a case, the energy (i.e. kinetic energy) is essentially always zero for the large mass and ((4)) is no longer relevant. One cannot change the outcome e_i by shifting e_j , because e_j for the large mass is always 0 and $p(0)$ is always the same. Thus, there is no stochasticity in such a scenario because there is no stochasticity in the kinetic energy of the large mass or large mass linked to $V(x)$. As a result, determinism does hold in such cases, but not in the collisions of molecules, we argue.

One may also argue that billiard ball collisions may be predicted to a certain degree based on where a hit occurs, but these are examples which are far away from the stochastic scale of gas

molecule collisions and quantum $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$ collisions. We note that the classical notion of entropy was microscopically applied to gas molecules and these exist at a quantum scale and quantum stochasticity may still be present in such collisions. If that is the gas, the classical notion of Shannon's entropy from a classical gas may actually follow from quantum stochasticity, we suggest.

Conclusion

A microscopic definition of entropy seems to be associated historically with a classical gas. Even though the gas molecules are quantum, they exist at high temperatures and are usually considered as interacting classically through conservation of energy and momentum. These conservation laws, however, do not allow for a full deterministic treatment of the interaction. If one suggests that one need only consider the conservation laws (momentum and energy for an elastic collision), which is often done in Newtonian collision problems, then given e_1, e_2 and p_1, p_2 , one does not know that exact outcome, only that it must conserve energy and momentum. Sometimes it is suggested that using only the conservation laws is a deliberate approximation and that if one wanted to, one could include full detail and describe the interaction in a completely deterministic manner at any scale.

We disagree because for $dp/dt = \text{Force}$, there exists a scale at which dt is not 0. We argue that a force hit may occur at a time in dt with a certain probability. Ultimately one has stochastic collisions at this scale. We suggest that one may actually find dx and dt from special relativity, i.e. $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$. A probability of the form $\exp(i f(x)) \exp(i g(t))$ (because there is no real weight for a free particle because there is no distribution of a real quantity like energy as in a gas) must show dx , and dt . A Lorentz invariant result is $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$. This result, however, shows that product probabilities for the same $e_1 + e_2 = E$ and $p_1 + p_2 = p$ (one dimension) represent a uniform distribution (i.e. a minimal information one).

We suggest that these same ideas apply to a classical gas which consists of quantum molecules, albeit at high energies. We suggest that one cannot deterministically predict the outcome of collisions for this reason and that is why one assumes $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$. This leads to $p(e_i) = C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$ which forms the same uniform product distribution as the free particle quantum case from which it follows (we argue). As a result, the idea of Shannon's entropy, which may be created from the result $p(e_i) = C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$, may be thought of as following from the uncertainty inherent in quantum free particle elastic collisions. These collisions consider only the minimal information, i.e. one does not have a quantum particle collide with a $V(x)$ which requires an analysis using the Schrodinger equation. Rather, one has the case in which only energy and momentum conservation laws need to be considered. This corresponds to the physical situation of high temperature.